

A Study of SHA Algorithm in Cryptography

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BACKGROUND THEORY

SHA-2 (Secure Hash Algorithm 2) is a set of cryptographic hash functions designed by the United States National Security Agency (NSA). They are built using the Merkle–Damgård structure, from a one-way compression function itself built using the Davies–Meyer structure from a (classified) specialized block cipher. SHA-256 and SHA-512 are novel hash functions computed with 32-bit and 64-bit words, respectively. They use different shift amounts and additive constants, but their structures are otherwise virtually identical, differing only in the number of rounds.[1]

John the Ripper (Dictionary Attack Method) John the Ripper is the free password cracking software tool. Initially developed for Unix operating system. It is run in different platform such as DOS, Win32, BeOS.

Fig –John the Ripper tool usage

ABSTRACT

Today, security is important on the network. Therefore, the security is provided by the nature of one way functions, which is a key component of SHA (Secure Hash Algorithms). The purpose of this paper how to use SHA-256 and SHA-512 from SHA-2 algorithms. SHA-2 is a family of two similar hash functions with different block sizes known as SHA -256 and SHA-512. They differ in the word size;SHA-256 uses 32-bits words where SHA-512 uses 64-bit words. There are also truncated versions of each standard, known as SHA-223, SHA-384, SHA-512/224 and SHA-512/256. These were also designed by the NAS.

KEYWORDS: hash file; SHA-256; SHA-512; John the Ripper tool

INTRODUCTION

Cryptographic hash functions are utilized in order to keep data secured by providing three fundamental safety characteristics: pre-image resistance, second pre-image resistance, and collision resistance. The cornerstone of cryptographic security lies in the provision of pre-image resistance, which makes it hard and time-consuming for an attacker to find an original message given the respective hash value. This security is provided by the nature of one way functions, which is a key component of SHA.

SHA-256 is faster on 32-bit processors. SHA-512 is faster on 64-bit processors. SHA-512 has 25% more rounds than SHA-256. SHA-256 performs 64 rounds of its compression function over 512 bits at a time. SHA-512 performs 80 rounds of the compression function over 512 bits at a time. SHA-512 beats SHA-256 for hashing anything more than 16 bytes of data at a time.

SHA-256 Algorithm

Fig- SHA-256 processes in Algorithm

A. Using Python Program to generate Hash form in SHA-256

Fig2 Python code for execute hash file

